

Additions

325

The phrase 'old number' refers to the number of the ms. in the I. O. M. sequence, which is in fact correct.

1051. Sirat Ibn Hisham. II. The second part of Ibn Hisham's Biography of Muhammad. Size 10 in. by 6 3/4 in.; foll. 195. (Presented by Sir W. Muir, March 7, 1877) (Old no. 3202)

1052. Talkhis Sirat al-nabi. Abridgement of Ibn Hisham's Biography of Muhammad, by Ahmad b. Ibrahim b. Abd al-rahman al-Wasiti. Size 12 in. by 4 1/2 in.; foll. 243. (Presented by Sir W. Muir, Jan. 31, 1877) (Old no. 3195)

1053. Sirat of Ibn Hisham. Abstract a translation & analysis. Size 10 1/2 in. by 8 in.; foll. 205. (Presented by Sir W. Muir, Jan 31, 1877) (Old no. 3202^a)

1054. Katib el-Wakidi (also called the Tabatkat) by Muhammad Ibn Saad [See Muir's Life of Mahomet, Vol 1, p. xcvi] Size (Presented by Sir W. Muir, Jan 31, 1877) (Old no. 3203)

1055. Sirat of Ibn Saad Katib al Wakidi. Translation in abstract by Sir W. Muir. Size 10 1/2 in. by 8 in.; foll. 402. (Presented by Sir W. Muir, Jan 31, 1877) (Old no. 3203^a)

1056. Yarikh Jabari. IV. Size $9\frac{3}{4}$ in.

by $6\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 221.

3208

(Presented by Sir W. Muir, Mar. 12, 1877)

(Old no. 3208)

3201

~~1057. Kitab al-Ansab. Size 9 in. by 5 in.~~

See ~~the~~ D. P. M. cat. of Persian mss., no. 168, p. 74.

~~foll. 164.~~

~~(Presented by Sir W. Muir, Mar. 7, 1877)~~

~~(Old no. 3201)~~

1058. Kitab el minhaj fil fikh.

3204

Size $8\frac{1}{2}$ in. $5\frac{3}{4}$ in.; foll. 231.

(Purchased April 13, 1877)

(Old no. 3204)

1059.

Hashshaf of Lamakshari. Commentary on the Coran. Size 12 in. by 8 in.; foll. 341.

3199

II, 1088

(Presented by Sir W. Muir,

(Old no. 3199)

1060.

Sir Khawarizmi. Size $9\frac{1}{2}$ in. by 6 in.; foll. 431.

3197

(Presented by Sir W. Muir, July 18, 1877)

(Old no. 3197)

1061.

Hal-ul-Mujiz. Size $10\frac{1}{2}$ in. by $5\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 343.

3144

(Purchased from the executors of the Marquess of Hastings)

(Old no. 3144)

1062.

Ul-a'yat el marumiyat. Size $7\frac{3}{4}$ in. by $4\frac{1}{4}$ in.; foll. 193.

3451

(Prohibition book?)

(Old no. 3451)

1063. Kitab Malaki Ben Ans, a System of Muhammadan Religion. Size 8 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 109. (Purchased April 10, 1877) (Old no. 3194)
1064. Halila wa Damma. Size 8 in. by 5 1/4 in.; foll. 136. (Purchased Mar. 29, 1878) (Old no. 3186)
1065. Sharh el Wikayah. Size 8 3/4 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 362. (Purchased April 13, 1877) (Old no. 3198)
1066. Multaka 'l-abhar or the meeting of Seas. Size 7 3/4 in. by 5 in.; foll. 134. (Purchased April 10, 1877) (Old no. 3196)
1067. Mucktasar de Aly Ben isa ben D. et Sol. sobre las prac. del Islam. Size 8 in. by 5 in.; foll. 40. (Purchased March 29, 1878) (Old no. 3187)
1068. Maimonides' Delalet ul hairen. (Hebrew character) Size 13 1/2 in. by 9 1/2 in.; foll. 19. (Presented by Lord Northbrook, Mar. 15, 1877) (Old no. 2300)
1069. Koran (Arabic & Chinese) Size 8 1/4 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 60. (Presented by M. Gabbett June 7, 1883) (Old no. 3140)

1070. Sharh Hidāyat-al-hisnat. (Maid-
budhis C. on the Hidāyah.) (Two other
copies of this work are referred to by
D. Lohr; see nos 487 & 488) Size 8 7/8 in.
by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 161. (Old no. 1595.)

1071. Mirat'ul qamar. Size 11 1/4 in.
by 9 1/2 in.; foll. 209.
(Purchased Nov. 30, 1875.) (Old no. 3452.)

1072. _____ . Size 10 3/4 in.
by 6 3/4 in.; foll. 274.
(Purchased Nov. 30, 1875) (Old no. 3221)

1073. Tareekh Khummese, History of
Muhammad by Houssein Ben Ahmad
Vol I. Size 9 in. by 7 1/2 in.; foll. 334.
(Old no. 3449)

1074. _____ . Vol II. Size 8 7/8
in. by 7 1/2 in.; foll. 335.
(Purchased Nov. 30, 1875) (Old no. 3450)

1075. Muntakhabu-l-Lughat. Abridgment
of the Dictionaries, Lexicon, Arabic, &
Persian by Abdu-l-Rashid Hamadani.
Size 9 1/2 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 238.
(Purchased March 7, 1901)

1076. Euclid. Size $9\frac{1}{2}$ in. by $6\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 120
(Exhibition book)

1077. Calligraphy. Size $9\frac{1}{2}$ in. by $5\frac{7}{8}$ in.;
foll. 25 (Exhibition book)

1078. Account of the names of the Potentates
who erected the various Mosques in &
about Ahmedabad. * (Presented by
Najee Suddrodeen Hoossein to the Govt
of India, Jan. 12, 1891.) Size $11\frac{3}{4}$ in. by
 $4\frac{3}{4}$ in.; foll. 14 (joined together & folded
in book form) * (Arabic & Persian)

1079. Kuran. Part of the Kuran. Size $3\frac{1}{5}$
in. by $2\frac{1}{5}$ in.; foll. 84. II iv 2216

1080. Lakhrāh dar 'ilm i ta 'būr i Khwāb.
Interpretation of dreams. (Old no. 1688).
Size $9\frac{1}{3}$ in. by $6\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 214.
(Apparently overlooked by D. Lott in 1870)

1081. Treatise on Muhammadan Law, according
to the Hanafite School. The title is wanting,
as is also the name of the author. Size $6\frac{1}{4}$ in.
by $8\frac{3}{4}$ in.; foll. 112; lines 21.
(Presented by Sir F. Goldsmid, Feb. 11, 1903.)

Mai-
to other
by
8 7/8 in.
1595
1 1/4 in.
3452
10 3/4 in.
221
of
Hamood
ll. 334.
3449
Size 8 7/8
3450
Judgment
c. 8
ann.

1082. Dasidah Durdah. (Arabic
Hindustani & Pers.) Size $9\frac{1}{4}$ in. by 5 in.; foll.
2109 50; lines 8 + 13. (Old no. 2109)
(College of St William, 1825)
(apparently overlooked by D. Lott)

1083. Manual of Prayers π . (with Persian
head-lines) Size $9\frac{1}{2}$ in. by $4\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 24;
3675 lines 11. (Exhibition book)
IN 2215

~~1084. Miscellanea.~~

~~Ethical religious poem by Sa'ib al-Din.
Shams al-iman.
Arabic Grammar. (Portions)
work in celebration of the birth of Muhammad.
Risalah yata'allahu bi-al-tajwid.
Muhammad's interview with Gabriel.
Poem in honour of 'Abd al-Zahir.
Description of the Muhammadan Paradise.
Risalah al-jatā fi al-amal bi-al-rub al-
madatū.
Risalah fi al-amal bi-rub al-jab. By
Muh. ibn Abi al-Khadir.
Kitāb fi arkan al-nikāh wa al-kāmil.
Poem in honour of Muhammad.
Sūfi Saints (fragment)
Account of the Sūfi Saint 'Abd al-Zahir
Gilanī. (fragment)~~

~~1084 (Continued)~~

~~{ Magāsid al-nikāh.
Religious Ablutions & Purifications.
Fragment.~~

~~Size 8 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 115; lines 7-23.~~

~~Old No. 2420~~

~~(Overlooked by D. Loth)~~

1084. Miscellanea.

2420a

1. Kitāb fī arkhān (abridgement)
2. Shams al-īmān.
3. Nifāyat al-ganū' fī-l'amal bi-l rub 'al naqtā'
4. Risālah fī-l'amal bi rub 'al jayb.
5. An ethical religious poem by Lām al-Dīn.
6. Fragments of works relating to Muhamma-dan Saints.
7. Portions of a work in praise of Muhammad
8. Magāsid al nikāh.
9. Fragments of grammatical works.
10. Risālah yata' allagu bi-l tajwid.
11. An account of Muhammad's interview with the angel Gabriel & the angel of Death.
12. Portion of a work on religious ablutions & purifications.

Size 8 in. by 5 3/4 in.; foll. 129; lines 7-23.

Old No. 2420

(Overlooked by D. Loth)

Bib. Leyden

1085. Fragment of a book of Prayers
 2484 a Size 6 in. by 4 in.; ff. 8. (Formerly in Pers. MS 2484); lines
 9 & 10. (overlooked by D. Lott)

1086. Risālah Ma'mūlah by Sayyid Qutb
 al-Dīn Muhammad Khān. (A Commen-
 tary on Khūlasat al-Hisāb. (See No. 958)
 3086 b (M^c Kenzie, No. 92 (Wilson's Catalogue,
 Vol. II. p. 118. (VII).
 Size $4\frac{7}{8}$ in. ^{by 5 in.}; foll. 29; lines 7 & 8.
 (Old No. 3086.)
 (overlooked by D. Lott)

1087. Mushtabih al-nisbah by Abū
 Muhammad Abd al-Ghanī b. Sa'īd al-
 Aẓdī. Size $12\frac{1}{4}$ in. by $7\frac{3}{4}$ in.; foll. 185; lines 17.
 3700 (Purchased 16 Jan. 1906)

1088. Alf Sailah wa Sailah. (Part of the story
 of Saif al-Mulūk, & of Hasan al-Basrī.)
 3678 Size $8\frac{1}{2}$ in. by $6\frac{1}{4}$ in.; foll. 130; lines 19-24.
 (Blot M.S.)

1089. Majma' al-Ghanāyā, a collection of
 notes on the Jāghūjī. (Foll. 4-end) (Arabic
 3671 intermixed with Persian)
 (Preceded by some pages in Persian, viz.
 fol. 1. Fragment of a work on Saif.
 " 2(a) l. 8. Treatise on Nahw.

1089 (continued)

fol. 2(b) l. 4. A prescription.

" 3(a) Catechism on the use of Bis-
-millāh.)

Size 8 1/2 in. by 6 in.; foll. 38; lines 13-20.

(Mc. Kenzie, No 82)

1090

3685 Muthār al-gharām ilā yū'arat al-
zuds w-al-Shām, by Shihāb al-Dīn Abū
Mahmūd Ahmad b. Muhammad al-
Maqdisī. Size 7 1/8 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll.
101; lines 19.(Purchased Feb. 9, 1905)

1091

3697 Dalā'il al-Khairāt by Abū 'Abd Allah
Muhammad b. Sulamān al-Garzūlī.
Size 4 1/2 in. by 4 1/4 in.; foll. 105; lines 10.

(Formerly in the possession of Prof. Palmé)

3697

II v 2214

(Purchased Jan. 11, 1906)

1092

3698 Sharh al-Zasidah Ibn 'Abdūn by
Abū Marwān 'Abd al-Malik b. 'Abd
Allāh b. Badrūn. Size 5 7/8 in. by 4 in.;
foll. 256; lines 13.(Purchased Jan. 11, 1906)

1093

3699 Kitāb al-Darā'ilā al-maqām al-asrā',
by Ibn al-'Arabī, with a commentary by his
Pupil Jamā'il b. Sandakūn. (dated 1009 A. H.)

334
1093 (continued)

Size $8\frac{1}{4}$ in. by $5\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 198 (two of them blank); lines 21.

(Purchased Jan. 11, 1906)

3696
1094 Sharh al-Shawāhid, a commentary on the verses quoted by al-Lamādhsharī in his Washshāf, by Muhibb al-Dīn Jaqī al-Dīn al-Hamawī. Size 8 in. by $5\frac{3}{4}$ in.; foll. 266; lines 15.

(Purchased Jan. 11, 1906)

3694
(a, b)
1095 al-durar al-kāminah fi a'yān al-mi'at al-thāminah, by Shihāb al-Dīn Ahmad b. 'Alī called Ibn Hajar (Biographical dictionary of famous men who died in the 8th cent. H) 2 Vols. Size $12\frac{1}{4}$ in. by 8 in.; foll. (I, 291, II, 271); lines 17.

(Purchased June 20, 1905)

3695
1096 al-kāfi fi 'ilm al-dīn, by Muhammad b. Ya'qūb al-Kulīnī. (Kitāb al-talāq to the end) Size 12 in. by $7\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 374; lines 26.

(Purchased June 20, 1905)

3703
1097 al-jauhar al-rafi' by 'Abd al-Rahmān al-'Alawī al-Tabidī, with a commentary by the author. Size $12\frac{1}{4}$ in. by $8\frac{1}{2}$ in.; foll. 903; lines 24-26.

(Purchased March 28, 1906)

1098

Mudārik al-tawzīl, a commentary on the Zur ān by Abū al-Barakāt 'abd allāh b. Ahmad al-Nasafī.

3704

6½ in.; foll. 568; lines 25.

Size 9¾ in. by

II i 1130

(Purchased March 28, 1906)

1099

Ma'ālim al-tawzīl, a commentary on the Zur ān, by al-Hasan b. Mas'ūd al-Farrā' al-Baghawī.

3705

lines 29.

Size 11⅓ in. by 7½ in.; foll. 469;

II i 1082

(Purchased March 28, 1906)

1100

Misbāh al-ūlūm fī ma'rifat al-hayy al-qayyūm, by Ahmad b. Muhammad al-Rasās, with a commentary by Ibrāhīm b. Yahyā al-Suhūti.

3706

Size 8½ in. by 6¼ in.; foll. 42; lines 19-30.

(Purchased March 28, 1906)

1101

A Commentary on Ibn Mālik's Yashīl al-fawā'id.

3707

Size 9 in. by 6½ in.; foll. 174; lines 13-25.

(Purchased March 28, 1906)

1102

al-faraj ba'd al-shiddat, (based on the work of the same name by Abū 'Alī al-Hasan b. 'Alī al-Yarūbkhī).

3708

Size 7⅔ in. by 6 in.; foll. 152; lines 19.

(Purchased May 29, 1906)

1103. Collection of treatises on grammar etc.

- 3709 ✓
1. Al-i'rāb an qawā'id al-i'rāb by Abd Allāh b. Yūsuf Jamāl al-Dīn Ibn Hishām, with a commentary by Khālid b. Abd Allāh al-Ayharī.
 2. Mi'at Kāmilah fī sharh mi'at āmilah, by Hājji Bābā b. Ibrāhīm al-Jūsiyyawī.
 3. A commentary on Ibn Hishām's Latr al-radā.
 4. Al-'unqūd fī 'ilm al-nahw, with a commentary by Abū Ja'far 'Umar b. Ibrāhīm b. 'Abd al-Ghanī.
 5. Al-Kawakib al-sāti' by 'Abd al-Rahmān Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūtī.

Size 8 $\frac{1}{3}$ in. by 6 in.; foll. 125; lines 13-26.

(Purchased May 29, 1906)

1104.

- 3749
- Sayyid 'Alī Muhammad al-Bāb, Bayān 'Arabi. Size 8 in. by 5 in.; foll. 29; lines 19.
- (Presented by M. A. L. M. Nicolas.)

1105.

- 3720
- Al-munabbihāt by Ibn Hajar. Size 6 $\frac{6}{8}$ in. by 4 $\frac{7}{8}$ in.; foll. 33; lines 13-15.
- (Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

1106.

- 3721
- Three tales (all imperfect): -
- (i) The Ten Warriors. (foll. 2-36(a).)
 - (ii) The Duenna, the Interpreter & the King's son. (foll. 36(b)-39(b).)
 - (iii) Haigār al-hakīm. (foll. 40(a)-fin.)

1106 (continued)

Size 8 1/2 in. by 6 1/2 in.; foll. 48; lines 18-22.
(Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

1107.

Al-Lailah wa Lailah. (From the beginning to the story of Nur al-Din & his son Badr al-Hasan.) Size 9 in. by 6 in.; foll. 149; lines 25.
(Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

3722

1108.

al-ashbah wa'l-nadhā'ir by Ibn Mujāwir. Size 9 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 295; lines 17.
(Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

3723

1109

Al-risālah al-Zushayriyyah by Abū l-Lāsim 'Abd al-Karīm al-Hawāziri al-Zushayrī. Size 10 in. by 5 3/4 in.; foll. 302; lines 17.
(Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

3724

II 1220

1110.

al-mughnī fī sharh al-mūjiz, by Sadīd al-Dīn al-Nāzarūnī. Size 9 1/2 in. by 5 1/2 in.; foll. 154; lines 17-22.
(Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

3725

1111.

Glosses on al-Dawwānī commentary on al-Taftāzānī's Tahdhīb al-mantiq. Size 8 1/4 in. by 4 2/3 in.; foll. 182; lines 21 & 22.
(Purchased Mar. 18, 1907)

3726

1112.

3754

Kitāb Dujā' al-ummah fi adillah al-
-a'ummah, a treatise on feqh, compiled either
by 'Uthmān ibn Fūdū or one of his followers,
early in the 19th century.

At the end of the MS. are foll. of prayers.

Size 22 x 16 cm; foll. 186; lines 10-24.

(Purchased Mar. 17. 1909)

1113.

3668

Sermons. By a Christian author
XVIIth century.

Size 22 x 16 cm; foll ; lines

II W 2221

(Purchased Mar 19. 1909)

1114.

II W

2189

Three controversial treatises: -

a. Tuhfat al arif fi al radd ala ahl
al salib, by Abd Allah b. Abd Allah al
Taryuman, Against Christianity.

3728

2192

b. al Saif al mahdud fi al radd ala
al yahud, by Abd al Haqq al Islam
surnamed al Mahdi, Against Judaism.

2190

c. Manafi al sulban fi al radd ala
abadah al anthan, by Abd al Haqq
al Khazraji. Against Christianity.
A. H. 1252 (A. D. 1836) Foll
22 x 16 cm; lines.

1115.

3757

a. al Kafiyah fi al nahw, by Ibn al
Hafib. A. H. 1114 (A. D. 1703) 18 x 11 cm;
Foll 88; lines

1115. (continued)

b. A tract on Logic, in Persian. Foll 5.
(Purchased Mar. 19, 1909)

1116. Three astronomical treatises: -

a. Kitab dar heat, by Ali al Qushji
Persian. Foll 1-49.

b. Al Sufair fi al hiah, a compendium
of astronomy, by Ghiyath al Din
Mansur b. Sadr al Din Muhammad
al Dashtaki al Shirazi (died A. H.
948) Foll. 50-85.

c. Disalah fi al amal bil rub al
mujayyab, a manual of the use
of the sunuated quadrant, without
author's name. Arranged in a
Muqaddimah & 20 Babs. Foll. 66-7
XVII th century (tracts a & b by the same
hand). Foll. 69, 18 x 11.5 cm; lines
(Purchased Mar. 19, 1909)

3758

1117.

Al Irshad fi al nahw, a compendium of
Arabic grammar by Shihab b. Shams b. Umar
al Lawuli al Daulatabadi (died A. H. 849)

XVII th century. Foll. 123, 20.5 x 15 cm; lines

(Purchased Mar. 19, 1909)

1118.

Lataif al mangush fi mahasin al Hubush,
a treatise on the excellencies of the Abyssinian race,
by Abu al Maali Ala. al Din Muh. b. Abd Allah
al Duhari al Makki. Composed in A. H. 991

XVII th century. Foll. 131, 20.3 x 13 cm; lines
(Purchased Mar. 19, 1909)

3755